

Experimental Study of Different Sloshing Regimes in a Horizontal Cylindrical Tank under Lateral Excitation.

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ABSTRACT

This article presents an experimental characterization of the behaviour of the free surface of a liquid contained in a horizontal cylindrical tank with flat end walls and an aspect ratio of $L/D = 1.14$. The cylinder is subjected to forced oscillations in the horizontal plane with fixed amplitude and frequency, followed by a second stage in which the cylinder is held stationary and the liquid undergoes free damped oscillations. The third control parameter in these experiments was the liquid filling level in the tank. Time-resolved measurements of the lateral forces acting on the cylinder and of the axial moment were recorded, along with video recordings for each test case.

Within the range of excitation frequencies allowed by the experimental setup, the two dominant frequencies controlling the response of the fluid free surface were identified. These frequencies agree with the theoretical and experimental values predicted for the first two antisymmetric modes for all filling levels. When the driving frequency approaches either of these natural frequencies, intense fluid motion develops, generating jets and splashes that disrupt the continuity of the free surface. Each of these resonance bands is flanked by relaxation regions in which the free surface remains compact. The damping coefficients associated with the different filling levels were evaluated, the spectra of the force signal with and without external excitation were compared, and the occurrence of a beating phenomenon was observed. The study systematically maps the sloshing regimes as a function of excitation parameters and filling levels, providing practical insights for predicting free-surface behaviour in industrial and cryogenic tank applications, and supporting the validation of numerical models.

Keywords: Sloshing (573) — Hydrogen (343) — Tanks (739) — sloshing regimes (847) — Isothermal (1583) — horizontal cylindrical tanks (1476)

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for a clean and environmentally friendly transportation industry requires the storage and transport of large amounts of liquid fuels at cryogenic temperatures, which entails several technological challenges that demand highly focused research. A typical example is the use of cryogenic hydrogen as a fuel in the civil aviation industry, which represents one of the key technological challenges currently facing society. One of the fundamental components for the innovative developments that are taking place in the transport industry is the fuel tank. Challenges such as the design and optimization of cryogenic hydrogen storage in the aircraft industry are currently among the most advanced topics in applied fluid mechanics. The effects of the movement of large fluid masses on the stability of their containers or the overall vehicle are well-known even for missile operations *J. L. MacCarty & D. G. Stephens (1960)*. Understanding the thermo-fluid-dynamic phenomena occurring inside a cryogenic tank is a primary objective in transport engineering. Unlike other fields, the dynamic behaviour of aircraft induces complex sloshing phenomena and heat and mass transfer processes between the different phases of hydrogen and/or the tank walls. This understanding requires experimental evidence of the phenomena occurring inside the tank, which is normally

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40 obtained using scaled versions of full-scale tanks.

41
42 One of the primary objectives of this research is to understand how the liquid phase of a cryogenic fluid exchanges
43 heat with its surroundings, which consist of the tank walls and the upper gaseous phase, both generally at slightly
44 higher temperatures. Similar cases are found in the hydrogen transport industry [H. N. Abramson \(1966\)](#). For this
45 type of thermo-fluid-dynamic study, it is generally assumed [M. E. Moran et al. \(1994\)](#) that the problem is moderately
46 decoupled with respect to its fluid-dynamic and thermal components. Although the fluid motion, particularly the free
47 surface structure, governs the thermal evolution of the fluid and its heat and mass exchange, these thermal phenomena
48 have little influence on the evolution of the free surface. This is equivalent to assuming that the thermal evolution
49 of the multiphase fluid depends on the dominant sloshing regime, but not the other way around. This assumption
50 allows the sloshing regimes to be studied independently of subsequent thermo-fluid-dynamic analyses, for which prior
51 classification of the sloshing regimes is highly advantageous. According to [S. W. Colville et al. \(2024\)](#), understanding
52 wave kinematics is crucial for analysing the thermodynamic effects of sloshing, which can lead to pressure drops in
53 non-isothermal cryogenic fuel tanks. Therefore, this work aims to carry out a comprehensive study over a range of
54 amplitudes and frequencies typically employed in experimental studies at the scale of cryogenic transport tanks.

55
56 Thanks to the exhaustive experimental campaign conducted by Prof. Angel Martín at UPM to quantify the impact
57 of liquid load and its effect on the stability of trucks [Ángel Luis Martín López \(2013\)](#), we have an unpublished
58 database that deserves thorough analysis. This investigation focused on common tank geometries and allowed the val-
59 idation of numerical simulations of fluid-vehicle interactions. Although the research focused on liquid transportation
60 in trucks, most of its findings remain applicable to the current context of several transport industries. To identify the
61 main parameters defining the different sloshing regimes, an extensive experimental campaign was conducted. A large
62 number of sloshing scenarios typically found in liquid transport industries were analysed.

63
64 To systematically investigate sloshing behaviour across different scales, it is crucial to identify the principal dimen-
65 sionless parameters that govern the system. For isothermal sloshing, these scaling parameters represent the dominant
66 forces and partition the flow into distinct sloshing regimes, providing a structured basis for interpreting the system's
67 dynamic response under varying conditions. The scaling analysis relevant to this phenomenon has been thoroughly
68 addressed in several handbooks and foundational studies [F. T. Dodge et al. \(2000\)](#); [M. Dreyer \(2006\)](#); [R. Ibrahim \(2005\)](#);
69 [O. Faltinsen & A. Timokha \(2009\)](#). The resulting dimensionless groups account for the influence of tank
70 geometry, external excitation, and the dynamic characteristics of the fluid [S. M. Hasheminejad & H. Soleimani \(2017\)](#);
71 [D. Lomen \(1965\)](#); [H. F. Bauer \(1964\)](#); [J. Miles \(1984\)](#); [A. Royon-Lebeaud et al. \(2007\)](#).

72
73 The state of the art in this field includes numerous studies, summarized by [S. Sankar et al. \(1992\)](#), on sloshing in
74 tanks conducted since the 1960s across various domains, including spacecraft, large stationary tanks, channels, ships,
75 and trucks. The main disadvantage of experimental investigations is the limited range of excitation amplitudes and
76 frequencies for large-scale tanks, due to the power constraints of the excitation equipment. Theoretically, linear wave
77 theories assume potential flows, inviscid fluids, and linear kinematic conditions at the free surface. These theories
78 agree well with experimental data, but only for small motion amplitudes, as noted by [S. Abril-Pérez et al. \(2005\)](#).
79 This has led to the use of numerical solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations, along with continuity and free-surface
80 conditions, as a better approximation, as highlighted by Sankar et al. [S. Sankar et al. \(1992\)](#), to reproduce fluid
81 behavior under dynamic excitations. In the sloshing flows analyzed, it is important to distinguish between frequencies
82 far from resonance, where some linear approximations may remain valid, and frequencies close to resonance, where
83 nonlinear effects—such as the formation of hydraulic jumps at low filling levels—become more significant. Other
84 phenomena, such as breaking waves or impacts on the tank roof, introduce dissipation and damping, disrupting the
85 linearity of the process and altering the resonance frequencies.

86
87 Several tank designs have been studied in the literature, such as upright cylindrical tanks under lateral accelera-
88 tions, which have been extensively investigated in spacecraft stability analyses [H. N. Abramson \(1966\)](#). Additionally,
89 rectangular and spherical tanks, widely investigated in naval applications [R. Ibrahim \(2005\)](#), as well as 2D tanks
90 examined in fundamental studies due to their relevance in certain sloshing scenarios encountered in civil aviation. In
91 this work, we focus on the horizontal cylindrical tank, as it appears to be the configuration most commonly used in

innovative projects within the cryogenic transportation industry [HASTA project \(2024\)](#).

In the specific context of horizontal cylindrical tanks, the frequency values for the first antisymmetric sloshing mode have been established for circular sections by Budiansky et al. [B. Budiansky \(1960\)](#) using linear potential flow theory. This theoretical approach was experimentally confirmed by [J. L. MacCarty & D. G. Stephens \(1960\)](#), who conducted experiments with four different circular-section cylindrical tanks, varying their aspect ratio L/D from 2 to 5.81 and filling heights h/D from 0.04 to 0.949, using water as the working fluid. An important experimental study of the natural sloshing frequency in tanks was conducted using scaled models by Strandberg et al. [L. Strandberg \(1978\)](#), comparing different tank geometries such as circular, elliptical, and "super-elliptical" tanks with various filling levels.

[P. Mciver \(1989\)](#); [D. Evans & C. Linton \(1983\)](#); [X. Deng & M. Tait \(2008\)](#); [Y. Han et al. \(2021\)](#) applied the linearized theory of water waves to numerically determine the frequencies of free oscillations under gravity for an arbitrary amount of fluid in a horizontal circular cylindrical container, as well as the three-dimensional sloshing of fluid in a spherical tank. [G. Popov et al. \(1993\)](#) determined the amplitude and damped natural frequencies of fluid sloshing within a circular shell subjected to an acceleration simulating constant rotation. The steady-state solutions were obtained analytically based on hydrostatic equilibrium, while the transient solutions were derived through numerical integration of the Navier–Stokes equations, continuity, and momentum equations for a fluid with a free surface, achieving errors similar to those of the steady-state analysis. This study identifies the main parameters as the Reynolds number, the magnitude of the excitation acceleration, and the filling level. The influence of the Reynolds number on the magnitude and frequency of sloshing is minimal when $Re > 10^3$, as typically encountered in the transport industry, and it primarily affects slow-oscillating highly viscous fluids with $Re < 10^3$. [J. Martínez-Carrascal & L. González-Gutiérrez \(2022\)](#). Popov confirmed that larger excitations increase the magnitude of the moment and lateral forces, while decreasing the sloshing frequency. Finally, it was observed that increasing filling levels reduce the sloshing amplitude but increase the natural frequency. In general, the methods used in [G. Popov et al. \(1993\)](#) are only applicable to small excitation amplitudes and are not valid for low filling factors, shallow water conditions, or tanks with complex geometries. They also fail to capture impacts or account for viscous dissipation, which must be introduced through experimental parameters.

[S. A. Karamanos et al. \(2009\)](#) investigated externally induced sloshing in horizontal cylindrical tanks, assuming ideal and irrotational flow, small-amplitude free-surface elevations, and employing appropriate trigonometric functions for the sloshing potential. An efficient methodology was proposed for externally induced sloshing through the calculation of the corresponding sloshing frequencies. In parallel, [O. M. Faltinsen & A. N. Timokha \(2010\)](#) studied two-dimensional forced liquid sloshing in a circular tank using the multimodal method, assuming an incompressible, inviscid liquid, irrotational flow, and linear free-surface conditions. This linear multimodal sloshing solution fails under steady-state, nearly resonant conditions. A later work by [O. M. Faltinsen & A. N. Timokha \(2012\)](#) presents an alternative representation of the velocity potential for the liquid sloshing problem in a two-dimensional circular tank, which facilitates an effective approximation of the natural sloshing modes for all tank filling levels. More recently, and in good agreement with previous studies, [S. M. Hasheminejad & H. Soleimani \(2017\)](#) proposed a theoretical formulation based on linearized potential theory to study three-dimensional natural sloshing in a partially filled, horizontally circular cylindrical tank of finite span. In conclusion, numerous articles have computed or measured the natural frequencies of the problem studied here, achieving a high level of agreement between theoretical and experimental investigations.

Particular geometric variations of cylindrical tanks were studied by [H. Luo et al. \(2023\)](#), focusing on the sloshing behaviour and dynamic characteristics of liquid in a horizontal Cassini tank. This horizontal tank consists of hemispherical cavities at both ends connected by a central cylinder. The radius of each spherical cavity is $R = 0.1$ m, and the diameter and height of the central cylinder are both 0.2 m. The experimental inputs are the magnitude and frequency of the external excitation (2.5–4.0 Hz) and the liquid filling level ratios. The forces and torques generated by liquid sloshing in non-equilibrium states were measured experimentally. A narrow aspect-ratio horizontal cylinder ($L/D = 0.1$) was used by [S. W. Colville et al. \(2023\)](#), who presented an experimental study characterizing the fluid response of isothermal water in a horizontal cylinder with a fill level of 30%. The same geometry was used in [S. W. Colville et al. \(2024\)](#) to investigate Faraday waves in a horizontal circular tank under vertical excitation, where the

Figure 1. Section and length of the tank (right) and photograph of the tank (left) used during the experiments. The orange line indicates the platform and tank oscillatory movement.

effect of the density ratio was also considered.

In F. Florin et al. (2025) investigated isothermal sloshing in a small-scale horizontal cylindrical tank. An experimental campaign was conducted using a horizontal cylindrical tank with $L/D = 1.5$, partially filled with deionized water and subjected to vertical sinusoidal excitation. The objective was to map the liquid response regimes across the excitation frequency–amplitude range of interest. Ten distinct sloshing modes were observed within the 4-10 Hz excitation frequency range. The modal frequencies and damping coefficients were obtained using a sloshing surface identification algorithm. An experimental study combining the use of a horizontal cylindrical tank and non-isothermal sloshing was conducted by F. Monteiro et al. (2025), describing the induced thermal mixing inside the tank subjected to vertical acceleration.

We also briefly mention the various experimental approaches used in the past to support and excite a tank. These devices include suspended tanks functioning as pendulums R. Ibrahim (2005), tanks mounted on guides for lateral excitation (N. Pal et al. (2001); J. A. Romero et al. (2006); J. Romero et al. (2007); J. Romero Navarrete (2003); P. Werner & C. J.T. (1961); W. Zhanqi et al. (1995)), tanks mounted on pneumatic bearings that allow rolling excitation (T. Su & S. Kang (1984a,b, 1986, 1989); L. Delorme et al. (2005)) and devices capable of providing six degrees of freedom for tank movement are also available (R. C. B. Wendel G. R. (2002)). Regarding excitation mechanisms, a wide variety exists, ranging from free excitation devices—which impose an initial position and allow the tank to oscillate freely—to forced excitation controlled by electric motors or exciters.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the theoretical framework of the problem; Section 3 details the experimental setup, the parameter space, and the experimental methodology; and Section 4 presents the results obtained during the experimental campaign and subsequent post-processing.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

The general objective of this study is to investigate the different sloshing regimes in a horizontally oriented circular cylinder of length L and diameter D , partially filled with a liquid of density ρ . The coordinate axes of the cylinder are defined at the end closest to the camera position, where the X -axis is oriented parallel to the cylinder axis, the Z -axis is oriented opposite to gravity, and the Y -axis is orthogonal to the XZ plane (see Figure 1). In this configuration, the tank of total volume V is partially filled with a liquid volume V_L , while the remaining volume consists of air. The filling level FL is defined as the volumetric ratio between the liquid volume and the total cylinder volume, $FL = V_L/V$. Due to the significant density ratio between the liquid and air, the inertia of the ullage phase is considered negligible. The

175 tank is subjected to a harmonic sway motion, indicated by an orange arrow along the Y -axis in Figure 1. Apart from
 176 the transient intervals, the imposed excitation follows the equation:

$$177 \quad y = A \sin(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

178 where y is the horizontal sway coordinate, A is the excitation amplitude, $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular sloshing frequency,
 179 f is the excitation frequency, and t denotes time. In summary, the degrees of freedom of the experiment are:

- 180 • The excitation amplitude A
- 181 • The excitation frequency f
- 182 • The filling level FL

183 The dimensional analysis of the problem has already been performed, allowing the estimation of the relevant dimen-
 184 sionless groups derived from the governing equations prior to conducting experiments or numerical simulations (see
 185 J. Martinez-Carrascal & L. M. Gonzalez-Gutierrez (2021, 2022); M. D. Wright et al. (2020)). The main conclusion
 186 from these studies is that the present problem depends primarily on the geometric aspect ratio L/D , the filling level
 187 V_L/V , and the Froude number $gD/(A^2\omega^2)$, and only weakly on the Reynolds and Weber numbers in the present
 188 context, where the working fluid is water and the characteristic time and length scales are fixed. The introduction of
 189 these dimensionless numbers enables the comparison of different experimental setups involving various tank sizes and
 190 fluid properties, thereby facilitating the achievement of fluid-dynamic similarity. In this framework, the excitation is
 191 selected to preserve Froude similarity, thereby ensuring free-surface dynamics comparable to those of the full scale
 192 case, see a similar approach in J. Martinez-Carrascal & L. González-Gutiérrez (2022). Consequently, the scaling of
 193 the different variables involved in the problem to larger scales can always be performed a posteriori. This approach
 194 enables their application during the design phase of experimental tanks and in the selection of appropriate working
 195 fluids. In other words, the scaling analysis should be regarded as an experimental tool for quantifying deviations from
 196 real-case scenarios.

197
 198 The forces and torques induced by fluid sloshing are determined by the pressure distribution acting on the tank walls.
 199 In general, the hydrodynamic pressure of a liquid contained in a rigid tank can be decomposed into two components:

- 200 • One component is directly proportional to the tank acceleration and is associated with the portion of the fluid
 201 that moves in unison with the tank, behaving as a rigid body.
- 202 • The other component, known as convective pressure, is associated with the sloshing motion of the free surface.
 203 This component can be modelled using a series of mechanical analogies, such as mass-spring systems or a mass
 204 suspended from a pendulum R. Ibrahim (2005).

205 When the liquid motion is planar and linear, it is possible to develop a simulation methodology based on a series of
 206 masses elastically connected to the container by springs and dampers, or alternatively, on a series of simple pendulums.
 207 In general, mechanical equivalent models provide a good approximation of the liquid dynamics when the excitation
 208 frequency is far from resonance. In S. A. Karamanos et al. (2009), a methodology is proposed for computing the
 209 portion of the total liquid mass M_L that contributes to sloshing. This mass is decomposed into the convective
 210 (sloshing) masses M_{nC} ($n = 1, 2, 3$), associated with free-surface elevation, and the impulsive mass M_I , which follows
 211 the container motion. It is shown that, in linear sloshing cases, consideration of only the first sloshing mass is
 212 sufficient to represent the dynamic behaviour of the liquid-container system with good accuracy. In the case of nearly
 213 full containers ($FL > 75\%$), the impulsive mass is approximately equal to the total liquid mass ($M_I \approx M_L$), and
 214 consequently sloshing effects are negligible. Conversely, at low filling levels, the impulsive mass M_I tends to zero,
 215 indicating that almost the entire fluid mass participates in sloshing. Near resonance, these linear models are no longer
 216 valid, and nonlinear analyses must be employed. In general, three fundamental regimes of fluid behaviour can be
 217 identified, as defined by Ibrahim R. Ibrahim (2005):

- 218 • Linear regime, characterized by small-amplitude oscillations, in which the fluid free surface remains planar and
 219 rotates about the center of gravity of the free surface. This regime can be described by a linear differential
 220 equation, equivalent to that of a simple pendulum under the small-angle approximation, where $\sin \phi \approx \phi$.

Figure 2. Main experimental setup: the filled tank, aluminium plate and load cell

- Large-amplitude oscillation regime, in which the free surface no longer exhibits planar oscillations. This regime can be described by a weakly nonlinear differential equation, analogous to that of a simple pendulum undergoing large oscillations. Consequently, the restoring term can be approximated as $\sin \phi \approx \phi + \frac{\phi^3}{3!}$
- Nonlinear regime, in which nonlinearity is sustained by strong accelerations caused by hydrodynamic impacts between the free-surface fluid and the tank walls.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. *Experimental campaign.*

This subsection describes the experimental campaign that served as the basis for the subsequent PhD thesis presented by Ángel Martín [Ángel Luis Martín López \(2013\)](#). A photograph of the manufactured cylindrical tank, with the superposed reference system used for the experiments and subsequent analysis, is shown in Figure 1. The dimensions of the cylindrical tank with flat end caps are: diameter $D = 438\text{mm}$ and length $L = 500\text{mm}$. This scaled tank corresponds to a 1:5 scale model of tanks typically found in several industrial applications, which have a cross-sectional area of 3.7m^2 at full scale. The cylindrical tank walls were made of 10mm thick methacrylate to allow optical access while maintaining minimal structural deformation during the experiments. The working liquid is water mixed with a fluorescent dye to facilitate flow visualization and imaging.

The test rig comprised a table that served as a support for the exciter and for the tracks along which the tank slides during its sinusoidal motion, see Figure 2. The two tracks were mounted on the table and supported by four ball rollers to reduce vibration and friction induced by the motion (see Figure 3). To generate the oscillatory motion of the tank, a servo-controlled hydraulic cylinder was used to drive the table supporting the sliding tank. On top of the rollers, a 1m^2 , 2cm thick aluminium plate was installed (see Figure 3). This plate served a dual purpose: first, to homogenize the motion of the two rows of rollers along the tracks; and second, to provide a rigid support and anchorage for the load cell and the tank.

The selection of the amplitude and frequency ranges is constrained by the rig construction and the characteristics of the servo-controlled hydraulic cylinder. Accordingly, three excitation amplitudes are tested: $A = [5, 10, 15]\text{mm}$.

Natural frequency	Non-dimensional natural frequencies $\lambda_n = \omega_n^2 R/g$	Dimensional frequency(Hz)
First	$\lambda_1 = [0.9988, 3.0362]$	$f_1 = [1.06, 1.55]$
Second	$\lambda_2 = [4.6142, 8.3695]$	$f_2 = [2.29, 2.63]$
Third	$\lambda_3 = [7.785, 12.864]$	$f_3 = [2.97, 3.81]$

Figure 3. Left: Sliding system of the rig (red). Right: Servo controlled hydraulic cylinder and displacement sensor.

247 For the intermediate amplitude $A = 10, \text{mm}$, seven filling levels are tested, $FL = [12.5, 25, 37.5, 50, 62.5, 75, 87.5]\%$,
 248 whereas only three filling levels, $FL = [25, 50, 75]\%$, are investigated for the other two amplitudes. For each combina-
 249 tion of excitation amplitude and filling level, the frequency is varied within the interval $f \in [0.4, 2.6]\text{Hz}$ using uniform
 250 steps of 0.2Hz , resulting in a total of 13 excitation frequencies.

251

252 In order to anticipate how many natural frequencies may be excited within the investigated frequency range, the
 253 values reported in the literature must be dimensionalized. Table 3.1 presents the nondimensional natural frequencies
 254 $\lambda_n = \omega_n^2 R/g$ corresponding to the first three antisymmetric modes, using values reported in S. A. Karamanos et al.
 255 (2009); S. M. Hasheminejad & H. Soleimani (2017). These frequencies are expressed as intervals ranging from the
 256 minimum value of λ_n up to the value corresponding to $FL = 87.5\%$. In the second column of the table, these
 257 intervals are dimensionalized and adapted to the present experimental setup in terms of frequency (Hz). According
 258 to the notation introduced by S. M. Hasheminejad & H. Soleimani (2017), different free-surface oscillation modes can
 259 be identified depending on the longitudinal and transverse excitation components: Antisymmetric–Antisymmetric
 260 (AA), Symmetric–Antisymmetric (SA), Antisymmetric–Symmetric (AS), and Symmetric–Symmetric (SS). In the
 261 present study, the excitation is purely transverse, and therefore predominantly two-dimensional modes are excited,
 262 corresponding to antisymmetric SA modes. A. Kolaei et al. (2015) provides a mathematical justification for why only
 263 antisymmetric SA modes are excited under lateral excitation of the container. During the experimental campaign, no
 264 stable symmetric modes were observed within the investigated frequency range. It is likely that vertical excitation is
 265 required to trigger SS modes, as discussed in S. W. Colville et al. (2024).

266

267 To obtain an accurate description of the sloshing regimes, it is important to note that the experimental frequency
 268 range, $f \in [0.4, 2.6]\text{ Hz}$, generally encompasses the first and second resonant frequency intervals, f_1 and f_2 , which
 269 correspond to antisymmetric modes. The only exception occurs for the case $FL = 87.5\%$, for which the second natural
 270 frequency exceeds the upper limit of 2.6 Hz . The third mode is not accessible within the capabilities of the present
 271 experimental facility.

272

273 On the previously mentioned plate, a triaxial load cell was installed to simultaneously measure the vertical force F_z ,
 274 the transverse horizontal force F_y , and the moment M_x induced by the oscillatory motion of the tank–liquid system.
 275 The load cell was manufactured by SixAxes, with a measurement range of $2500\text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$ for the moment M_x and 5000
 276 N for the forces F_y and F_z . The sensitivities were 1.176 mV/V for the moment measurement, and 1.856 mV/V and
 277 1.874 mV/V for the horizontal and vertical force measurements, respectively. To measure the transverse displacement,

278 a laser linear displacement sensor was installed on the rig. The sensor was manufactured by MEL and features a
 279 measurement range of 340 ± 100 mm with a sensitivity of 10 mm/V.

280
 281 To reduce noise in the force and moment signals, a third-order low-pass Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of
 282 25 Hz was applied. For image processing, a MATLAB routine was developed to identify all pixels within a predefined
 283 search range, defined by the target colour and detection tolerance. The contour of the detected region was then
 284 extracted by identifying image discontinuities, yielding a closed contour from which the enclosed area and its centroid
 285 were computed.

286
 287 For each combination of the problem's degrees of freedom (filling level, excitation frequency, and amplitude), the
 288 excitation procedure was applied consistently. The sequence of steps is summarized as follows:

- 289 1. Start of the data acquisition system.
- 290 2. Start of the tank excitation.
- 291 3. Start of the periodic excitation.
- 292 4. End of the periodic excitation.
- 293 5. End of the tank excitation.
- 294 6. End of the data acquisition.

295 These steps are illustrated in Figure 4. During steps 3 and 4, the periodic sloshing regime is analyzed, and the
 296 amplitudes of the torque and forces are recorded over a 20–30 s interval. The interval between steps 4 and 5 is
 297 employed to experimentally determine the natural frequencies and the wave damping factor.

3.1.1. *First natural frequency and Wave Damping factor*

300 Although several analytical approaches have been reported in the literature for computing or experimentally mea-
 301 suring the first natural frequency of horizontal cylindrical tanks with plane circular sections (see S. A. Karamanos
 302 et al. (2009); S. M. Hasheminejad & H. Soleimani (2017); J. L. MacCarty & D. G. Stephens (1960), among others),
 303 the natural frequency of the first sloshing mode was determined experimentally in this study. To this end, the tank
 304 was first excited transversely (Y direction) until a steady-state regime was reached. The excitation was then abruptly
 305 stopped (see Figure 4), allowing the liquid to oscillate freely. During this free-oscillation period, the force and moment
 306 signals were analysed to identify the natural frequencies.

307
 308 The damping factor was determined using the logarithmic decrement of the free-surface oscillation amplitude. Similar
 309 to the procedure used for the natural frequency measurement, the tank was excited at its resonant frequency until a
 310 steady state was reached, after which the excitation was abruptly stopped. The logarithmic decrement of the measured
 311 force or moment signals was then used to evaluate the damping. As noted by Ibrahim R. Ibrahim (2005), the damping
 312 decreases significantly with increasing liquid height, reaching a minimum at a fill factor of approximately 50%. This
 313 behavior occurs because, at low fill factors, wall friction dominates over the inertial forces of the liquid, resulting in
 314 higher damping values. Although measuring the logarithmic decrement for the first oscillation mode is straightforward,
 315 a simplified analytical approximation is often convenient to estimate the damping without the need for experiments or
 316 CFD simulations. For instance, Abramson et al. H. N. Abramson (1966) present a method for estimating the damping
 317 factor in vertical cylindrical tanks. The same methodology can be applied to other tank geometries, although the
 318 constants in the analytical models are available only for vertically oriented rectangular, spherical, and conical sections.

3.1.2. *Periodic excitation*

320 During sinusoidal excitation, the time evolution of the forces F_y , F_z , and the moment M_x is predominantly sinu-
 321 soidal, with additional harmonic components arising depending on the proximity of the excitation frequency to the
 322 natural sloshing frequencies. The dominant frequency of the output signals closely matches the excitation frequency
 323 for F_y and M_x , whereas it is approximately twice the excitation frequency for F_z .

Figure 4. Tank excitation process with indications of the different regions for study.

3.2. Hydrodynamic forces

The forces and moments measured by the load cells of the sloshing rig include not only hydrodynamic contributions but also inertial effects associated with the load cell and the gravitational components of the tank. These measurements are referred to as wet tests. To isolate the hydrodynamic forces—i.e., the action of the liquid on the tank walls—two separate experiments are required to separate the liquid contribution from the solid elements. Consequently, additional measurements, referred to as dry tests, were conducted at the same excitation frequencies and amplitudes with the empty tank. An additional advantage of these experiments is that they allow validation of CFD simulations. Since CFD results account only for the hydrodynamic forces, direct comparison with experimental data requires subtracting the forces and moments measured in the dry tests from those obtained in the corresponding wet tests.

Using the subscript LC to denote load-cell measurements and F for the hydrodynamic forces, Newton's law can be applied to describe the dynamics of a tank containing sloshing fluid:

$$\mathbf{F}_{LC} + \mathbf{F}_F + m\mathbf{g} = m\mathbf{a} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{F}_{LC} denotes the force measured by the load cell, \mathbf{F}_F represents the force exerted by the fluid confined in the tank, m is the mass of the solid components accelerated during the forced motion—namely, the methacrylate tank, the aluminum plate, and the load cell itself—and \mathbf{g} is the gravitational acceleration. The equation can be particularized for the dry case (superscript d) as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_{LC}^d + m\mathbf{g} = m\mathbf{a}^d \quad (3)$$

where in the dry case, the fluid force is absent, i.e., $F_F^d = 0$. In the wet case (superscript f), the tank contains a given filling level of fluid. Consequently, Equation (2) can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{LC}^f + \mathbf{F}_F^f + m\mathbf{g} = m\mathbf{a}^f \quad (4)$$

Subtracting Equation (3) from Equation (4) yields the hydrodynamic force acting on the tank:

$$\mathbf{F}_{LC}^f - \mathbf{F}_{LC}^d + \mathbf{F}_F^f = m(\mathbf{a}^f - \mathbf{a}^d) \quad (5)$$

where the hydrodynamic force, \mathbf{F}_F^f is given by:

$$\mathbf{F}_F^f = \mathbf{F}_{LC}^d - \mathbf{F}_{LC}^f + m(\mathbf{a}^f - \mathbf{a}^d) \quad (6)$$

consequently, when the tank accelerations measured in the dry and wet cases are nearly identical, $\mathbf{a}^f \approx \mathbf{a}^d$, the hydrodynamic force can be approximated as the difference between the load-cell measurements in the wet and dry cases:

$$\mathbf{F}_F^f = \mathbf{F}_{LC}^d - \mathbf{F}_{LC}^f \quad (7)$$

Analogously, Newton's law for angular momentum can be applied to describe the dynamics of a non-rotating tank containing sloshing fluid:

$$\mathbf{M}_{LC} + \mathbf{M}_F + \mathbf{OG} \times m\mathbf{g} = 0 \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{M}_{LC} denotes the torque measured by the load cell, \mathbf{M}_F represents the torque exerted by the fluid confined in the tank, and \mathbf{OG} is the vector from the load cell to the center of gravity of the moving solid components. As in the previous force analysis, the equation can be particularized for the dry and wet cases as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}_{LC}^d + \mathbf{OG} \times m\mathbf{g} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{LC}^f + \mathbf{M}_F^f + \mathbf{OG} \times m\mathbf{g} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Subtracting Equation (9) from Equation (10) yields the hydrodynamic torque acting on the tank:

$$\mathbf{M}_{LC}^f - \mathbf{M}_{LC}^d + \mathbf{M}_F^f = 0 \quad (11)$$

where the hydrodynamic torque is given by:

$$\mathbf{M}_F^f = \mathbf{M}_{LC}^d - \mathbf{M}_{LC}^f \quad (12)$$

as consequence, the hydrodynamic torque can be approximated as the difference between the load-cell measurements in the wet and dry cases.

4. RESULTS

4.1. First natural sloshing frequency

The article introduction, see section 1, provided a brief review of previous studies that calculated the natural frequencies of similar tanks, both from theoretical and experimental perspectives. Since there is good consensus on these values, it remains fundamental to experimentally measure them and confirm that certain resonance frequencies fall within our excitation range—namely, the first frequency corresponding to the first antisymmetric mode and the second frequency corresponding to the second antisymmetric mode. As explained in Section 3.1.1, this was achieved by exciting the tank at a constant amplitude (see steps 3–4 in Figure 4) until a steady-state regime was reached. The excitation was then abruptly stopped, allowing the liquid to oscillate freely (see steps 5–6 in Figure 4). Finally, the experimental value of the first sloshing frequency was determined using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the free-response signals.

The natural frequencies obtained from these measurements are presented in Figure 5, where the first frequencies were determined using both the force and axial torque signals. As expected, the first natural frequency increases approximately proportionally with the filling level in all cases, while the second natural frequency exhibits a minimum near the middle of the filling range. The first and second measured sloshing frequencies show excellent agreement with theoretical and experimental values reported in the literature (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. First(antisymmetric) and second(symmetric) resonant frequencies measurements based on the force and momentum signals. Comparison with other experimental J. L. MacCarty & D. G. Stephens (1960) and theoretical works S. A. Karamanos et al. (2009).

4.2. Damping factor

To evaluate the sloshing damping factor, the logarithmic decrement of the oscillation amplitude of the free surface is estimated. This is achieved by exciting the tank at its resonance frequency until a steady-state regime is reached, after which the excitation is abruptly stopped. Figure 6 shows the transverse force signal F_y during the free-oscillation phase following the sudden stop. The logarithmic decrement Δ between two successive peaks, A_n and A_{n+1} , is defined according to Equation (13). In addition, the damping ratio δ and the critical damping ratio ξ are introduced and defined by Equations (14) and (15), respectively.

$$\Delta = \log\left(\frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$\delta = \frac{\Delta}{2\pi} = \frac{2\pi\xi}{\sqrt{1+\xi^2}} \quad (14)$$

$$\xi = \frac{\delta}{\sqrt{4\pi^2 + \delta^2}} \quad (15)$$

All peak values of the free-response signal were considered in the calculation (more than 50 s of free oscillation in most cases). An exponential amplitude envelope was then fitted to the data, and the corresponding coefficients were estimated using a least-squares regression. The measured damping factors for the circular-section tank are plotted as a function of the excitation frequency for several filling levels in Figure 7. The largest variations in the damping coefficient are observed at the lowest filling levels.

Figure 6. Logarithmic decrement of an amplitude lateral force signal F_y during the free oscillation phase of the case $A=10\text{mm}$ $f=1.2\text{Hz}$ $FL=50\%$.

Figure 7. Damping ratios measured for each fill level

Figure 8. Snapshots of the flow at $A=5\text{mm}$ and $FL=25\%$. Left: the tank is excited with $f = 1.2Hz(f/f_1^{25\%} = 1.0292)$ Right: second natural mode $f = 2.6Hz(f/f_2^{25\%} = 1.105)$.

4.3. Study of the Sloshing Regimes

The main objective of this study is the characterization of the different sloshing regimes observed for various combinations of excitation amplitude, frequency, and filling level. The measured forces and moments are predominantly sinusoidal, with a dominant frequency equal to the excitation frequency, although they are modulated depending on the proximity of the excitation frequency to the resonance frequencies. The system response—namely the lateral and vertical forces (F_y , F_z) and the axial moment (M_x)—was analysed for both dry and wet configurations in the time and frequency domains. Among these signals, the most representative quantities associated with the liquid motion under the present excitation conditions are the lateral liquid force and the roll moment amplitude. These quantities are computed using Equations (7) and (12), respectively, and are subsequently plotted as functions of the excitation frequency for different filling levels and excitation amplitudes.

The excitation frequency is non-dimensionalized using the natural frequency corresponding to a 50% filling level ($f_1^{50\%}$). The lateral force and axial moment are non-dimensionalized using the reference quantities $F_0 = \rho U_0^2 D^2$ and $M_0 = \rho U_0^2 D^3$, respectively, where $U_0 = 2\pi A f_1^{50\%}$ is the characteristic velocity and the water density is taken as $\rho = 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$. In general, for all filling levels, the force and moment amplitudes exhibit maxima in the vicinity of the first and second natural frequencies.

Since the primary aim is to identify and characterize the different sloshing regimes—and to assess how free-surface behaviour may influence non-isothermal problems under similar conditions—it is essential to determine when the free surface remains compact and predominantly two-dimensional, and when it breaks due to emerging jets and splashing, leading to a fully three-dimensional flow. Accordingly, the analysis is divided into three parts, corresponding to the three excitation amplitudes tested.

4.3.1. Low amplitude tests $A = 5 \text{ mm}$.

When the lowest filling level is tested ($FL = 25\%$, $f_1^{25\%} = 1.166 \text{ Hz}$; see Figure 5), the liquid oscillates from one side of the tank to the other while remaining compact and essentially two-dimensional. The only exception occurs close to the first resonant frequency at $f = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$ ($f/f_1^{25\%} = 1.029$), where the free-surface elevation exceeds the tank radius and small liquid detachments are observed. For excitation frequencies above 1.8 Hz, second-order modes become visible, characterized by relative maxima at the centre of the free surface. Nevertheless, the free surface remains compact and no significant breaking is observed. Figure 8 shows representative snapshots of the free surface at $f = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$ and at the highest excitation frequency tested.

For a filling level of 50%, the first natural frequency increases to $f_1^{50\%} = 1.255 \text{ Hz}$, and the free surface remains compact and essentially two-dimensional for excitation frequencies below this value. When the excitation frequency approaches the first natural frequency, at $f = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$ ($f/f_1^{50\%} = 0.956$), the free surface rises along the tank perimeter to elevations higher than at the centre, generating liquid jets that subsequently fall under gravity. These jets induce intense

Figure 9. Snapshots of the flow at $A=5\text{mm}$ and $FL=50\%$. Left: the tank is excited with $f = 1.2\text{Hz}$ ($f/f_1^{50\%} = 0.956$) Middle: second natural mode $f = 2.2\text{Hz}$ ($f/f_2^{50\%} = 0.958$). Right: Maximum frequency excitation $f = 2.6\text{Hz}$.

Figure 10. Snapshots of the flow at $A=5\text{ mm}$ and $FL=75\%$. Left: the tank is excited with $f = 2.6\text{Hz}$ ($f/f_2^{75\%} = 1.046$). Right: excitation frequency $f = 2.4\text{Hz}$ ($f/f_2^{75\%} = 0.966$).

438 splashing, leading to a fully broken free surface. For excitation frequencies between 1.4 Hz and 2.0 Hz, the free surface
 439 recompacts and the second-order mode dominates the flow. At $f = 2.2\text{ Hz}$ ($f/f_2^{50\%} = 0.958$), longitudinal modes and
 440 three-dimensional effects emerge, again producing splashing. Finally, for the two highest excitation frequencies tested,
 441 2.4 Hz and 2.6 Hz, the free surface becomes compact once more, with higher-order two-dimensional modes governing
 442 the flow. Representative snapshots of the free-surface behaviour at $f = 1.2\text{ Hz}$, 2.2 Hz, and 2.6 Hz are shown in Figure
 443 9.

445
 446 When the filling level is increased to 75%, the first natural frequency rises to $f_1^{75\%} = 1.423\text{ Hz}$. Consequently, the on-
 447 set of free-surface breakup shifts to higher excitation frequencies and is first observed at $f = 1.4\text{ Hz}$ ($f/f_1^{75\%} = 0.984$).
 448 When the excitation frequency is further increased to 1.6 Hz, the free surface becomes compact again. A second
 449 breakup regime appears at higher excitation frequencies, above $f = 2.4\text{ Hz}$ ($f/f_2^{75\%} = 0.966$), where second-order and
 450 longitudinal modes develop in the flow. Representative snapshots of the free-surface behaviour at $f = 2.4\text{ Hz}$ and
 451 $f = 2.6\text{ Hz}$ are shown in Figure 10.

452
 453 A comparison of the different filling levels for the low-amplitude excitation case ($A = 5\text{ mm}$) is presented in Figure
 454 11 for both the lateral force and the axial moment. It can be observed that the 50% filling level yields the maximum
 455 lateral force and axial moment. This behaviour is commonly reported in sloshing studies J. Martinez-Carrascal & L.
 456 González-Gutiérrez (2021), as maximum impact requires both a sufficient liquid mass and enough free volume to allow

Figure 11. Non-dimensional horizontal force (left) and axial moment (right) versus non-dimensional frequency for different filling levels and excitation amplitude $A=5$ mm

457 acceleration and an increase in impact velocity. In addition, the first natural frequency increases with the filling level,
 458 as expected from Figure 5. After the first resonance, the flow response relaxes and subsequently increases again as the
 459 excitation frequency approaches the second natural frequency. This effect is more pronounced for the highest filling
 460 level, $FL = 75\%$. According to Table 3.1, the second sloshing mode lies within the interval $f_2/f_1^{50\%} \in [1.84, 2.12]$,
 461 depending on the filling level, which is clearly evidenced in Figure 11. Finally, for this excitation amplitude, the second
 462 peak is significantly less energetic than the first one for all filling levels, resulting in lower force and moment amplitudes.
 463

4.3.2. Middle amplitude tests $A = 10$ mm.

464
 465 For this intermediate excitation amplitude, the number of filling levels tested is increased to seven, allowing for a
 466 more detailed description of the flow behaviour. For the lowest filling level ($FL = 12.5\%$), the liquid moves as a rigid
 467 body and the free surface remains completely planar, compact, and two-dimensional until the excitation frequency
 468 approaches the first resonant frequency, at $f = 1.2$ Hz ($f/f_1^{12.5\%} = 1.067$). At $f = 1.2$ Hz, the planar free-surface
 469 structure is perturbed by lateral elevations reaching approximately the tank centre height, and small liquid jets occa-
 470 sionally form and rise along the tank perimeter. Between 1.8 Hz and 2.2 Hz, the onset of the second transverse mode
 471 is observed, characterized by clearly identifiable maxima and minima on the free surface. At $f = 2.4$ Hz, additional
 472 transverse modes are excited and the free surface becomes fully three-dimensional. For excitation frequencies greater
 473 than or equal to 2.6 Hz, higher-order modes are present; however, a significant reduction in free-surface deformation
 474 is observed.
 475

476 In contrast to the low-amplitude case, for $FL = 25\%$ the free surface breaks at $f = 1.2$ Hz ($f/f_1^{25\%} = 1.029$), and
 477 lateral liquid jets impact and splash onto the bulk of the free surface. As the excitation frequency is further increased,
 478 the free surface recompacts and remains stable until $f = 2.2$ Hz ($f/f_2^{25\%} = 0.935$), where significant free-surface
 479 deformations are again observed and breakup occurs. At higher excitation frequencies, the free surface exhibits
 480 three-dimensional behaviour, although with relatively small deformations.
 481

482 When the filling level is increased to 50%, the flow remains compact and essentially two-dimensional up to $f = 1.2$
 483 Hz ($f/f_1^{50\%} = 0.968$), at which point detached jets appear and violent splashing is observed. Small travelling waves
 484 along the free surface are also present, producing a horizontal force modulation that is absent in the dry case. Figure
 485 12 shows a comparison of the wet and dry signals for $f = 1$ Hz and $FL = 50\%$. The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of
 486 the wet signal identifies both the excitation frequency and the first natural frequency near $f = 1.25$ Hz.
 487

488 This beating phenomenon is observed for all excitation frequencies below the first resonance ($f < f_1$) and is particu-
 489 larly relevant at low or medium filling levels, where the sloshing impulsive mass M_I is small compared to the total
 liquid mass. In contrast to the low-amplitude case ($A = 5$ mm), for $f = 1.4$ Hz some impelling jets are still generated

Figure 12. Left: Wet and dry horizontal forces for $A=10\text{mm}$, $FL=50\%$ and $f=1\text{Hz}$. Right: Fast Fourier transform of the Wet horizontal signal.

alternately from both sides. The flow recomacts within the frequency interval $[1.6, 2.0]$ Hz, but breaks up again for frequencies greater than or equal to $f = 2.2$ Hz ($f/f_2^{50\%} = 0.958$). The beating phenomenon can be explained as follows. For excitation frequencies relatively close to the natural frequency, e.g., $f = 0.8$ Hz, the fluid response exhibits the classical beating behaviour (see Figure 13). This can be interpreted as a signal with an angular frequency equal to the average of the excitation and the free-surface oscillation frequency, as discussed in O. Faltinsen & A. Timokha (2009). Spectral analysis confirms this interpretation: during forced excitation, both frequencies are present, the lower corresponding to the free-surface waves and the higher to the excitation. After the forced excitation is stopped, the free-decay process dominates and only the natural frequency remains.

When the excitation frequency is very close to the first natural frequency, both the spectral content and the time evolution of the wet force change significantly, see Figure 14 for $f = 1.2$ Hz and $FL = 50\%$. The spectrum exhibits peaks corresponding to the excitation frequency and its higher-order harmonics only. In the time domain, the wet force signal shows no modulation, but the maximum force values are characterized by two distinct peaks. These correspond to the complex interaction of the waves with the circular tank walls: the first peak arises from the initial water-wall impact, and the second from the subsequent splashing of water onto the central free surface under the influence of gravity. This particular force profile is referred to as a “churchroof” shape by D. Peregrine (2003), and it is commonly observed during violent wave impacts. Figure 14 illustrates this behaviour.

When the excitation frequency exceeds the first natural frequency, for example at $f = 1.4$ Hz, modulation in the wet force signal reappears. The spectrum exhibits two main peaks: one corresponding to the first resonant frequency and another at the excitation frequency. In addition, higher-order frequencies appear as a double peak around $f \approx 4.1$ Hz, resulting from the double-peak structure observed at the force maxima. Figure 15 shows the spectrum and time evolution of the wet force, where the double peaks at each maximum clearly indicate the presence of detached jets impacting the free surface. A small increase in excitation frequency to $f = 1.6$ Hz results in a very relaxed flow, with the spectrum showing only the excitation frequency and its harmonics, while the first natural frequency is barely visible. At $f = 1.8$ Hz, the flow remains compact, and the spectrum displays the excitation frequency; for the first time, the second natural mode at f_2 appears. In both cases ($f = 1.6$ and 1.8 Hz), the liquid force exhibits very little modulation, and no double peaks are observed at the maxima, as detached jets are absent. At $f = 2$ Hz, the flow continues to be compact, and the spectrum presents a single isolated peak at the excitation frequency. When the frequency reaches $f = 2.2$ Hz ($f/f_2^{50\%} = 0.958$), very close to the second natural frequency, double peaks at the force maxima appear again due to splashing. For excitation frequencies above $f = 2.2$ Hz, the spectrum of the unforced signal shows that the second natural frequency has a larger amplitude than the first.

Figure 13. Top: time evolution of the lateral force F_y when the beating phenomenon is present during the forced oscillation. Bottom: corresponding spectral analysis of the upper parts.

523 For a filling level of 75%, a compact flow regime is observed only at frequencies lower than or equal to 1 Hz. From
 524 $f = 1.2$ Hz ($f/f_1^{75\%} = 0.843$) onwards, lateral jets appear, resulting in a complete breakup of the free surface. This
 525 behavior persists up to $f = 1.6$ Hz, where the flow transitions to a compact three-dimensional regime. This regime
 526 remains until frequencies equal to or greater than $f = 2.2$ Hz ($f/f_2^{75\%} = 0.886$), at which point free-surface breakup
 527 occurs again.

528

529 For a filling level of 85%, free-surface breakup is not observed until the excitation frequency reaches $f = 1.4$ Hz
 530 ($f/f_1^{85\%} = 0.902$). At higher excitation frequencies, lateral jets form and the free surface breaks up. It is noteworthy
 531 that for frequencies below 2 Hz, the jets are mainly tangent to the tank perimeter (first mode dominant), whereas at
 532 higher excitation frequencies, the jets rise vertically from central positions (second mode dominant).

533

534 The results for this intermediate amplitude are summarized in Figure 16, from which conclusions similar to those
 535 obtained at low amplitude can be drawn. Two frequency regions can again be identified where the flow exhibits
 536 particularly violent dynamics, corresponding to the first and second antisymmetric excitation modes. In the region
 537 near $f/f_1^{50\%} \approx 0.95$, the jets are exclusively lateral, and the free surface remains relatively flat. In contrast, in the
 538 region $f/f_1^{50\%} \in [1.75, 1.8]$, high free-surface elevations also appear in the central area. Representative snapshots of
 539 both modes (first and second antisymmetric) for FL = 50% are shown in Figure 17. For the largest filling level (FL
 540 = 85%), the tank is nearly full, and the force and torque curves tend to approach the parabolic response expected for
 541 a full tank. The filling level of 62.5% generates the largest lateral force and torque, observed at a frequency of 1.2 Hz.
 542 In general, filling levels between 50% and 75% produce the most significant dynamic effects due to sloshing.

543

544 As mentioned in Section 3.1, the videos recorded during each experiment were analyzed using image processing
 545 software capable of detecting the pixels corresponding to the liquid region. The contour of the liquid region is identified
 546 as a closed section, from which the area and the center of gravity are calculated. When the flow is very violent, with

Figure 14. Top left: Time evolution of the wet and dry cases $A=10\text{mm}$ $FL=50\%$ and $f=1.2\text{Hz}$. Top right: Time evolution of liquid force. Bottom left: Fast Fourier transform of the wet force signal. Bottom right: snapshot of a typical impact.

547 jets and splashes, accurately determining the free surface becomes extremely challenging, and optical methods often
 548 fail, as illustrated in Figure 18 for a compact versus a splashing flow. Consequently, our technique is applied only to
 549 flows where the free surface remains compact. As a result, Figure 19 shows the evolution of the horizontal displacement
 550 of the liquid centre of gravity and the water height at the right side of the tank for two compact cases ($f = 0.8$ Hz
 551 and $f = 1.6$ Hz) with $FL = 50\%$.

552 4.3.3. High amplitude tests $A = 15$ mm.

553 For this highest excitation amplitude, the number of filling levels tested was reduced to three, focusing on the most
 554 representative cases. For $FL = 25\%$, the flow behaviour is very similar to that observed for $A = 10\text{mm}$. Although the
 555 maximum force and torque values are obtained at $f = 1\text{Hz}$, the free surface is not yet broken. For this filling level,
 556 the excitation frequency must be increased to $f = 1.2\text{Hz}$ ($f/f_1^{25\%} = 1.0292$) in order to observe free-surface breakup.

557
 558 For a 50% filling level, the free surface starts to break as expected at 1.2 Hz and also at 1.4 Hz. However, in
 559 contrast to the lower-amplitude cases, free-surface breakup appears again at $f = 2\text{Hz}$ ($f/f_2^{50\%} = 0.861$) and persists
 560 for all higher excitation frequencies. For a filling level of 75 %, the free surface remains compact only for excitation
 561 frequencies below 1 Hz, while for all higher frequencies free-surface breakup is observed.

562

Figure 15. Test at $A=10\text{mm}$ $FL=50\%$ $f=1.4\text{Hz}$. Right: Time evolution of liquid force. Left: Fast Fourier transform of the wet force signal.

Figure 16. Non-dimensional horizontal force (left) and axial moment (right) versus non-dimensional frequency for different filling levels and excitation amplitude $A=10\text{ mm}$

563 A global summary of these results is presented in Figure 20, where the two main maxima associated with the first
 564 and second natural frequencies are clearly identified. It is noteworthy that, for all excitation amplitudes, the maximum
 565 force and moment at the first natural frequency are obtained for a 50% filling level, whereas for the second natural
 566 frequency the 75% filling level produces the largest values.

567

568 4.4. Sloshing regime description

569 As observed in the analysis of the different sloshing regimes presented in Section 4.3, there are many qualitative
 570 similarities among them, all being clearly dominated by the two critical excitation frequencies f_1 and f_2 . Consequently,
 571 the detailed study of a representative filling level is sufficient to describe the main sloshing transitions observed across
 572 the different regimes. In what follows, we focus on a representative filling level of 50%, for which the lateral force is
 573 presented in non-dimensional form as a function of the non-dimensional excitation frequency, see Figure 21.

574

575 As discussed in Section 4.3, momentum signals are also available; however, they do not provide additional physical
 576 insight into the description of the sloshing regimes, therefore, only the lateral force F_y is considered here. Based on the

Figure 17. Snapshots of the flow at the two dominant excitation frequencies for $A=10$ mm and $FL=50\%$ Left: $f = 1.2Hz (f/f_1^{50\%} = 0.9681)$ and $f = 2.2Hz (f/f_2^{50\%} = 0.9582)$.

Figure 18. Examples of the result of the image processing software for the cases $A=10\text{mm}$ $FL=50\%$ $f=0.8$ Hz and $f=1.2$ Hz

577 analysis of the video recordings associated with each test case, several distinct sloshing regimes can be identified for a
 578 horizontally excited cylindrical tank with a 50% filling level. In Figure 22, three representative snapshots correspond-
 579 ing to the three excitation amplitudes are presented, from which four to five sloshing regimes can be distinguished
 580 depending on the amplitude. The two frequency regions where the lateral force reaches its maximum values can be
 581 clearly associated with resonant conditions. The first sloshing regime, common to all excitation amplitudes and filling
 582 levels, extends from the lowest excitation frequencies up to values close to the first resonant frequency, $f/f_1 \approx 1$.
 583 Within this range, the lateral force increases progressively until it reaches its maximum. The spatial structure of the
 584 antisymmetric mode associated with this first natural frequency is illustrated on the left-hand side of Figure 17.

585
 586 For excitation frequencies below resonance ($f/f_1 < 1$), the free surface remains compact and predominantly two-
 587 dimensional, with short-wavelength surface waves superposed on the characteristic linear oscillation. As the excitation
 588 frequency approaches the first resonant value, the free surface breaks and upward jets develop at both sides of the
 589 tank. For frequencies above the first resonance ($f/f_1 > 1$), a relaxation interval is systematically observed, during
 590 which the free surface becomes compact again and surface waves with wavelengths of the order of the tank radius
 591 dominate the flow.

Figure 19. Evolution of the horizontal displacement of the centre of gravity of the liquid(left) and water height level on the right part of the tank(right) for the cases $A=10\text{mm}$ $FL=50\%$ $f=0.8$ Hz and $f=1.6$ Hz

Figure 20. Non-dimensional horizontal force (left) and axial moment (right) versus non-dimensional frequency for different filling levels and excitation amplitude $A=15$ mm

592 A second critical frequency range is observed in the vicinity of the second natural frequency, $f/f_2 \approx 1$. Depending
 593 on the excitation amplitude, this regime is characterized by free-surface breakup, splashing, and the appearance of
 594 central upward jets. The rise and subsequent fall of these jets strongly perturb the free surface, leading to its fragmen-
 595 tation. The spatial structure of the antisymmetric mode associated with the second natural frequency is shown on the
 596 right-hand side of Figure 17. The distinction between the first and second resonant regimes is clearly reflected in their
 597 modal structures: the first mode exhibits a more linear behaviour, with high-energy jets rising tangentially along the
 598 tank walls, whereas the second mode displays a characteristic crown-shaped structure, with central jets appearing not
 599 only near the walls but also at the crown peaks, as illustrated in Figure 17.

600
 601 As mentioned in the introduction, one of the main objectives of this paper is to clearly identify the conditions under
 602 which the free surface remains compact and those under which it loses its structural integrity and breaks. Figure 22
 603 summarizes the different sloshing regimes observed for the three excitation amplitudes, filling levels, and excitation
 604 frequencies tested in the experimental campaign. Three basic free-surface states can be distinguished: a compact
 605 two-dimensional free surface, a highly distorted and broken free surface, and a compact three-dimensional free surface.
 606 Once again, the two resonant frequencies that dominate the sloshing dynamics are clearly identifiable. These regime

Figure 21. Non-dimensional lateral sloshing force F_y for 50% filling as a function of the different excitation frequencies. The different sloshing regimes are represented by pictures. Top: $A = 5mm$, middle $A = 10mm$, bottom $A = 15mm$.

maps provide practical and comprehensive information to predict the free-surface behaviour for any combination of the experimental parameters investigated in this study.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article presents an experimental investigation of the free-surface behaviour of a liquid confined in a horizontal cylindrical tank with flat end caps and an aspect ratio of $L/D = 1.14$, subjected to forced harmonic motion with constant amplitude and frequency. The third degree of freedom considered in the experiments is the tank filling level. As established in the literature on non-isothermal sloshing, the free-surface dynamics play a decisive role in governing heat and mass transfer between the liquid and gas phases; consequently, identifying the boundaries between the different sloshing regimes is of paramount importance. In the present experimental campaign, time histories of the lateral forces acting on the cylinder and the axial moment were recorded, together with synchronized video acquisitions for each test case. The damping factors associated with different filling levels were quantified, and spectral analyses of the force signals under forced and free-response conditions reveal the presence of a beating phenomenon, particularly when the excitation frequency is close to a natural frequency.

Within the range of frequencies accessible to the experimental facility, $f \in [0.2, 2.6]$ Hz, and excitation amplitudes between 5 and 15 mm, two resonance frequencies were identified as governing the behaviour of the liquid free surface. These frequencies were measured experimentally and found to match closely the theoretical predictions of the first two antisymmetric sloshing modes. Near these resonance frequencies, the fluid exhibits strong agitation, producing jets and splashing that disrupt the compactness of the free surface. Between the resonance regions, relaxation intervals occur where the free surface remains compact and predominantly two-dimensional.

Overall, this experimental campaign provides a comprehensive mapping of sloshing regimes in a horizontal cylindrical tank for varying excitation amplitudes, frequencies, and filling levels. The results identify the boundaries between compact, partially broken, and fully splashing free surfaces, offering practical guidance for the prediction of fluid behaviour in cryogenic or industrial transport tanks. These findings are particularly relevant for the design and validation of numerical models, including CFD simulations, where accurate representation of free-surface dynamics and fluid–structure interactions is critical.

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Figure 22. Sloshing regime identification graphs. Top: $A=5\text{mm}$, middle $A=10\text{mm}$ and bottom $A=15\text{mm}$

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